

Synthesis and Characterization of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II), Palladium(II) and Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with a Tridentate ONS Donor Schiff Base

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The reaction between 3-formylsalicylic acid and 2-aminothiophenol yielded the thiazoline (2) instead of the ligand H₃L (3). The treatment of metal acetate under refluxing condition rearranges the thiazoline structure to Schiff base complexes. The complexes of copper(II) (4), nickel(II) (5), zinc(II) (6), palladium(II) (7) and uranyl(VI) (8) have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, ir, uv-vis and thermal studies and partly by ¹H nmr, magnetic and cyclic voltammetric measurements.

We are interested for the last couple of years in the development of coordination¹ and organometallic² chemistry of Schiff bases having sulfur donor centres in a chelating environment. The Schiff base ligands are chosen for their versatility in transition metal chemistry³⁻⁶. The ligands derived from 3-formylsalicylic acid (3FSA, 1) and amines/diamines are quite interesting for their compartmental behaviour⁴. They can bind single⁵ or multiple^{4,6} metal ions to mimic bioinorganic, catalytic and magnetic materials. These have encouraged to study the reactions of a ligand derived from 3FSA and 2-aminothiophenol with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II} and UO₂^{VI}.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between 3-formylsalicylic acid and 2-aminothiophenol in methanol yielded the thiazoline (2) instead of Schiff base H₃L (3). It may act either polypodal NOO/SOO (in 2) or SNOO (in 3) or as tridentate ONS chelator. The ir spectrum shows a number of important vibrations at 1700, 3100 and 3350 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{COOH}, ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} respectively. The condensation is supported by the elimination of ν_{CHO} at 1660 cm⁻¹ in 3FSA (1). The absence of ν_{SH} and ν_{C=N} at ~2600 and ~1600 cm⁻¹ respectively, suggests benzthiazoline structure⁷. The ¹H

nmr spectrum also supports this formulation (vide infra).

In solution the thiazoline and the corresponding Schiff base may remain in equilibrium and in the presence of metal salts corresponding Schiff base metal complexes are produced. The complexes have been synthesised from methanolic solution of M(OAc)₂ or MCl₂ and NaOAc (2 eqv.) (M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II} and UO₂^{VI}) and H₃L at refluxing condition. The characterisation data are given in Table 1. The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit a typical band of coordinated imine^{8,9} at 1600–1620 cm⁻¹ and indicates rearrangement of thiazoline to Schiff base on metal complexation⁹. There are literature report on the ligating behaviour of thiazolines¹⁰. The stretch at 1710–1740 cm⁻¹ may be due to uncoordinated COOH. The blue-shifting from free ligand value (1700 cm⁻¹) is unclear and may be due to the combined effect of the rearrangement of the ligand structure, stereospecific interaction with coordinated metal ion and the presence of coordinated water. The spectra of the dehydrated salts of [Cu^{II}(HL)]₂ and [Ni^{II}(HL)]₂ exhibit ν_{COOH} at 1710–1720 cm⁻¹ along with other bands almost at undisturbed condition. Other hydrated complexes do not yield stable dehydrated products. The uranyl complexes (8) exhibit strong stretch at 900–930 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{O=U=O} and large number of heterocyclic ring vibrations at 1580–1200 cm⁻¹. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) is shifted from the ligand value 1505 cm⁻¹ to 1520–1535 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating nonbridged phenolato system⁴. The ν_{C-S} is blue-shifted by 15–25 cm⁻¹ in the Zn^{II} (6), Pd^{II} (7) and UO₂^{VI} (8) complexes from 685 cm⁻¹ in free ligand indicating thiolato bonding¹. In the Cu^{II} (4) and Ni^{II} (5) complexes ν_{C-S} is shifted by 40–70 cm⁻¹, suggesting the presence of thiolic sulfur bridge¹¹. Other bands of ν_{M-O}, ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-S} appear respectively at 530–580, 380–410 and 330–360 cm⁻¹.

The comparison of ¹H nmr spectra of the free ligand and diamagnetic complexes of Zn^{II} (6), Pd^{II} (7) and UO₂^{VI} (8) determine the structure of the complexes. The spectral data are set out in Table 1. The data reveal that 3FSA (1) exhibits δ(CHO) at 10.22 ppm which is absent in H₃L (2),

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL* AND ¹H NMR DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Colour	Metal% : Found/(Calcd.)	δ ppm ^a 4-H ^b	5-H ^c	6-H ^b	7-H	8-H	10-H ^b	11-H ^c	12-H ^c	13-H ^b
3FSA (1)			7.80	6.70	7.67						
H ₃ L (3)	Yellow		8.18	7.18	8.35	4.30 ^d	4.30 ^d	8.09	7.58	7.48	8.05
[Cu(HL)(H ₂ O)] ₂ (4)	Grey	16.28(18.01)									
[Ni(HL)(H ₂ O)] ₂ (5)	Brown	14.42(16.12)									
[Zn(HL)(H ₂ O)] (6)	Orange	15.64(18.43)	8.22	6.70	8.00	8.68 ^e		8.22	7.50	7.50	8.00
[Pd(HL)] ₂ (7)	Yellow		8.35	6.84	8.18	8.82 ^e		8.35	7.59	7.59	8.18
[UO ₂ (HL)(H ₂ O)] ₃ (8a)	Orange	38.54(40.00)	8.24	6.73	8.02	8.70 ^e		8.24	7.44	7.44	8.02
[UO ₂ (HL)(bpy)(H ₂ O)] (8b) ^f	Brown	30.14(33.29)	8.30	6.80	8.10	8.75 ^e		8.30	7.51	7.51	8.10
[UO ₂ (HL)(ophen)(H ₂ O)] (8c) ^g	Brown	30.18(32.21)	8.34	6.83	8.15	8.78 ^e		8.34	7.55	7.55	8.15

* All components gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^a solvent : CDCl₃ for 1, and DMSO-d₆ for 2, 6-8; ^b doublet, ^c triplet, ^d broad,

indicating the condensation. Again H₃L does not exhibit δ(CH=N) at its typical downfield position², besides a broad signal at 4.3 ppm (2H) which refers to thiazolic C-H and N-H and broadening attributes to electrical quadrupole moment of the nitrogen nucleus that induces a moderately efficient spin relaxation¹². The phenolic δ(O-H) appears at 8.95 ppm and COOH does not exhibit resonance that may be due to proton exchange with DMSO-d₆. The spectra of the Zn^{II} (6), Pd^{II} (7) and UO₂^{VI} (8) complexes exhibit sharp singlet at 8.6–8.8 ppm corresponding to δ(CH=N) and accounts the rearrangement of ligand to Schiff base (3). The ternary uranyl complexes give complex spectra due to appearance of other protons from heterocyclic bases.

The complexes are nonconducting, suggesting that the ligand is covalently bonded. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMF. Two bands at 296 and 390 nm in ligand solution are due to intra-ligand charge transfer transitions¹², π→π* and n→π* respectively. In complexes these bands are slightly red-shifted along with other bands. The Zn^{II} (6) and Pd^{II} (7) complexes show a weak shoulder at 420–430 nm. The uranyl complex (8a) exhibits two additional shoulders at 410 and 470 nm which may be ascribed to apical oxygen → f(U) and S → 5f(6d)/S → 5f(6d) transitions^{1,13}. Other complexes 8b, 8c exhibit additional bands in the uv region corresponding to coordinated bpy/ophen. [Cu(HL)(H₂O)]₂ (4) exhibits a weak transition at 600 nm corresponding to ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} which suggests the presence of five-coordinated geometry^{11,14}. [Ni(HL)(H₂O)]₂ (5) shows d-d transition at 517 and 675 nm corresponding to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}(F) respectively, which suggests grossly octahedral geometry. The zinc(II) (6), palladium(II) (7) and uranyl(VI) (8) complexes are diamagnetic. The copper(II) (4) and nickel(II) (5) complexes exhibit magnetic moment 0.54 and 2.18 B.M. per metal atom respectively, at 300 K. The dehydrated [Ni(HL)]₂ is

diamagnetic (0.08 B.M.) and indicates square-planar geometry, [Cu(HL)]₂ shows strong antiferromagnetic coupling (0.40 B.M.). The subnormal value indicates the partial spin pairing between two centres through thiolato bridge^{11,15}. The esr data of [Cu(HL)(H₂O)] (4) in polycrystalline and solution phase (DMF) at room temperature (300 K) exhibit four lines (⁶³Cu, I = 3/2) slightly anisotropic spectra at higher magnetic field. At liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) the spectrum gives axial type with g_{||} (2.278) and g_⊥ (2.092) with respect to DPPH marker. The trend g_{||} > g_⊥ > g_e (2.0037) suggests that the unpaired electron is localised in d_{x²-y²} orbital^{16,17}.

The cyclic voltammogram of the cupric complex (4) exhibits one quasireversible redox couple at E_{1/2} = 0.14 V (ΔE_p = 150 mV) and an irreversible peak at 0.7 V vs SCE. First response is reductive due to Cu^{II} → Cu^I and the second one is oxidative Cu^{II} → Cu^{III}. [Ni(HL)(H₂O)]₂ (5) shows quasireversible couple at 0.48 V (ΔE_p = 102 mV) that corresponds to Ni^{II} → Ni^{III} oxidation.

Thermal studies of the complexes were carried out in air under nonisothermal condition. The mass loss starts at 110° and continued upto 140°. The loss of coordinated water corresponds to two, four, one and three equivalents in 4, 5, 6 and 8a. The ternary complexes of uranium (8b and 8c) lose water at 130–150°, equivalent to one mole of H₂O, bpy and ophen loss at 300–450°. All the complexes reach at final residue as their oxides at 500–800°¹⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The solvents were distilled before use. 2-Aminothiophenol was obtained from E. Merck. 3-Formylsalicylic acid was prepared according to a literature procedure¹⁹.

The microanalysis were carried out by a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyser. Metal analyses were performed

iodometrically for copper, complexometrically for zinc, gravimetrically for nickel and uranium by standard procedures²⁰. The molar conductance of complexes in DMF ($\sim 10^{-3}M$) were determined at 27° using a Systronics 303 conductivity bridge. Thermal studies were carried out by a Shimadzu DT-30 analyser. Magnetic susceptibility was obtained from vibrating sample magnetometer (PAR 155). Cyclic voltammetric data were collected from EG&G PAR VERSTAT potentiostat with computer controlled CV instrument using Pt-bead working electrode, Pt-auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (sce) reference electrode, tetrabutylammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. The ir and electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 783 and Shimadzu uv 160 spectrophotometers respectively. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL JNM-GX 270 spectrometer. The esr spectra were recorded on a Varian 109 CE-line X-band spectrometer and fitted with quartz dewar at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT) in polycrystalline state and DMF solution.

Preparation of H₃L (3) : To a methanolic solution (15 ml) of 3FSA (1; 0.35 g, 2.11 mmol), 2-aminothiophenol (0.27 g, 2.16 mmol) was added dropwise and stirred magnetically for 1 h at room temperature. The solid formed was washed with cold methanol (2 × 5 ml) and dried under reduced pressure (70%), m.p. 320–22°.

Preparation of complexes : The metal acetate (5 mmol) or metal chloride (5 mmol) and sodium acetate (10 mmol) in methanol was added dropwise to a solution of H₃L (15 ml, 5 mmol) in the same solvent. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2 h on a steam-bath. The precipitated complex was filtered at hot and washed with methanol, ether, dried under reduced pressure, (55%).

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